

Factsheet

Mutual Learning Exercise - Science Communication in Research and Innovation

The Mutual Learning Exercise (MLE) “Science Communication in Research and Innovation”, inspired by the European Commission’ Policy Support Facility Challenge–MLE ([PSF–MLEs](#)), will be organised by the [COALESCE](#) project (set to build the [European Competence Centre for Science Communication](#)), aimed at **fostering national support for science communication by facilitating the joint exploration of specific research and innovation (R&I) policy challenges and opportunities**. It will do so by exchanging knowledge, success stories, experiences and barriers in fostering effective and trustworthy science communication, and support preparedness for future crises where science is key. This participatory and cooperative activity will equip high–level policy representatives (government, funders and RPOs) from the European Research Area (ERA) member states and beyond, with skills, tools and potential synergies to level–up science communication effectively in R&I national policies. Policy representatives will be paired with science communication research/practice representatives and members of the [COALESCE Hubs](#) from their own countries. This PSF–inspired MLE builds on the results of previous and ongoing PSF–MLEs on Citizen Science, Public Engagement, EU Missions and Bridging the gap between science and policy.

The following priority topics have been identified:

- **Topic 1:** Overview of the science communication landscape in national governance structures
- **Topic 2:** Social perception of science, trust and citizen engagement
- **Topic 3:** Rapid mobilisation of science communication and misinformation in times of crises
- **Topic 4:** Building skills & competences – a scicomm competence framework

Expected results:

- enhance R&I systems with dedicated and integrated science communication funding
- consolidating knowledge to improve science communication practice for all R&I actors
- encourage mainstreaming of quality science communication
- increasing science communication recognition and public support
- improve access and rapidly mobilised trustworthy science communication
- establish a science communication competence framework, across EU member states and beyond

The topic meetings will be chaired by:

Topic 1 experts: Cintia Refojo FECYT, Joana Magalhães SFC

Topic 2 experts: Joseph Roche TCD, Angela Monasor FECYT

Topic 3 experts: Carolina Moreno, Isabel Mendoza UVEG

Topic 4 experts: Ilda Mannino VIU, Aoife Taylor TCD

DG R&I Policy Officer: Mirella Rossi

COALESCE Project Officer: Irina Tiron

MLE Chair: Joana Magalhães and **MLE Co-Chair:** Isabel Mendoza

COALESCE hubs across Europe — ranging from academic institutions, such as Trinity College Dublin or Charles University Prague to specialized organisations like Wissenschaft im Dialog or Vetenskap & Allmänhet — will play a crucial role in shaping the EU's science communication landscape. These institutions engage in research, citizen science, media production, public engagement, and policy advising, each contributing unique expertise to the field. The European Competence Centre for Science Communication will strengthen this ecosystem by fostering knowledge exchange, best practice sharing, and joint initiatives. By bridging disciplinary, linguistic, and national divides, these partnerships enhance the impact and credibility of science communication across Europe, ensuring more inclusive and evidence-based public discourse on scientific issues.

Countries participating (9): Sweden

Indicative timetable

Kick-off meeting – KoM (online): 17th June 2025

Topic 1 meeting (F2F, Madrid): 24th September 2025

Topic 2 meeting (online): 1st-2nd week December 2025

Topic 3 meeting (F2F, *TBD*): March 2026, in collaboration with the [Inspiring ERA](#) project

Topic 4 and Final meeting (online): June 2026

Dissemination event (*TBD*) – September 2026

Format: in-person (F2F, 2 sessions in one full day) or online (2 sessions in 2 half days, except KoM in 1 half day session)

Structure: **Session 1** – presentation of topic by chairs, national case-studies by government representatives, experts and COALESCE Hubs stories; **Session 2** – participatory exercise

Outputs: 4 topic-wise short policy reports

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